

Relevance of Integrating Vedic Counselling in Modern Psychotherapy

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The objective of the present study is to assess the awareness and willingness among Counsellors to integrate Vedic Counselling in Psychotherapy. Vedic Counselling aims at integrating body, mind and consciousness at an individual level. It also aims at integrating individual, family and community at a collective level and integrating Humanity, Nature and Divine at a cosmic level. A survey research study is used where Counselling Psychologists are interviewed regarding the extent of awareness and application of Vedic Counselling in treating various psychological disorders. Through interviews and focus group discussions, data is qualitatively analysed and the perceptions of counselling psychologists regarding incorporating Yoga, Dietary modifications and Psycho spiritual counselling are discussed in the paper. The research study aims to establish the status of acceptance of Vedic counselling among mental health professionals and discusses the application of Vedic counselling strategies for health and well-being.

Keywords: Health and well-being, counselling psychologists, psychotherapy, psychospiritual counselling

Vedic Counselling is based on the ancient Vedic tradition and integrates the disciplines of *Yoga, Vedanta, Ayurveda, Jyotish, and Vastu* into a background *Vedic* counselling model.

According to Vedic scriptures, counselling has been a significant component of all Vedic disciplines and teachings since they were first developed thousands of years ago by the great yogis and rishis of the Himalayas (Frawley, 2017). The Guru, Pandit, Acharya, or Vaidya, who can be found in every village or community, is one of the many names and forms of this guiding role. They offer guidance in all facets of life, including suggesting yoga, meditation, mantras, healing techniques, and rituals to help people get through life's challenges and to enhance general well-being. In a counselling model, these conventional teaching responsibilities can be updated to take into account the circumstances of the contemporary world and its various guidance-based disciplines and methodologies. There are several specialist teachers, guides, counsellors or coaches in the world today, in health, psychology and spiritual fields.

Karmic counselling is another name for Vedic counselling, which aims to help us understand our karma and deal with it in a constructive way. It gives us the tools to constructively alter and eventually transcend karma completely, as well as an understanding of the nature of the karmic forces we must contend with. All facets of human existence are addressed in Vedic counselling, with transformative advice guiding us toward social, psychological, spiritual, and physical well-being. Vedic counselling offers comprehensive advice on how to spend our life in a way that will best enable the development of higher mental and behavioural capacities and ultimately result in self-realization. According to Vedic

counselling, our lives are a result of our karma, or personal deeds. We are ultimately accountable for the factors that have shaped who we are and what we experience, both individually and collectively. Since our lives are a product of our own karma, we must first accept responsibility for who we are and develop the ability to behave in a way that will help us get what we truly want. We all share responsibility for the things that happen in our lives, but we cannot hold anyone else responsible for who we are.

Dharmic advice on good living, right action, right relationship, and right consciousness is another definition of Vedic counselling. Instead of forcing a belief system, formula, or set of beliefs on anyone, its foundation is self-awareness, guiding us to a direct view of reality. It tackles all of life's objectives from the perspective of mental and physical health. An instructor of Vedic knowledge is known as a Vedic counsellor. As a "Vedic educator," he or she instructs others on Vedic methods for enhancing inner realization, societal peace, communication, and respect for the natural world. A Vedic counsellor can help you live a better life and become more conscious.

Additionally, a Vedic counsellor may specialize in one or more Vedic and Yogic disciplines, such as Ayurveda (Vedic medicine), Vedic astrology (Jyotish), Vedanta (Self-knowledge), Yoga in all of its branches, and Vastu (Vedic directional science). Different facets of the Vedic outlook on life are developed by all Vedic sciences. Ayurvedic psychology, out of all the specialties, acknowledges the connection between mental and physical health, recognizing that imbalances in one can have an impact on the other. The system acknowledges the importance of stress reduction, spirituality, diet, and lifestyle in preserving mental balance.

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Psychotherapy

Numerous worldwide organizations, professional associations, and other standard resources provide definitions and descriptions of the term psychotherapy. Essential overlaps serve as the basis for the practical definition of the important determinants of psychotherapy. The mooring point and the medium are two examples of such determinants. The grounding point is the human-to-human

therapeutic interaction, and "talk" is the medium through which therapeutic practices are transferred. Psychotherapy, then, is an intervention that uses "talk," which has therapeutic value, to treat mental problems. Science and research findings support the therapeutic efficacy of the "talk" and the therapeutic interaction. As a result, only well-supported psychotherapies can be suggested for the treatment of mental illnesses in a formal medical context.

Around the world, several psychotherapies have been created; some have succeeded, while others have not. The two main psychotherapies in the current context are psychoanalytic or psychodynamic therapy and Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (three generations), according to several professional organizations. Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) is the only psychotherapy that has strong empirical evidence for more than 80% of problems. Interpersonal psychotherapy, often known as evidence-based psychotherapy, has been shown to share a common cognitive-behavioural template with several other cognition-oriented psychotherapies. Individual psychopathology and its alleviation are the main emphasis of these psychotherapies.

Western psychotherapy models serve as the foundation for most of the Evidence-Based Psychotherapies (EBP) used in India. Since 2010, there has been a notable increase in the momentum for empirical therapy in research settings ($n = 12$ from 2000 to 2010 & $n = 68$ from 2010 to 2023). The CognitBehavioral paradigm is the most widely used EBP in India. There have been attempts to develop new methods for use globally as well as to duplicate the Western paradigm in Indian contexts.

Yoga therapy is one of the indigenous kinds of therapy that are becoming increasingly popular among practicing psychotherapists. While there are psychological benefits achieved through a technique-based practice, integrating yoga sutra-based counselling as a form of therapeutic sessions can provide additional long-lasting benefits.

Yoga-based counselling (YBC) is a component within the Integrated Approach to Yoga Therapy (IAYT), which aims at promoting holistic well-being by correcting the imbalances at physical, mental, and emotional (Putra, 2016). Yoga Based Counselling gives importance to the gunas: Sattvic guna (equilibrium), Rajasic guna (dynamic), and Tamasic guna (inertia), as well as the Physical constitution (Doshas) and the theory of the five levels of existence (Pancha kosha model). Imbalances in the gunas or the koshas can cause physical and psychological distress in an individual.

The goal of YBC is to provide comprehensive care to an individual by utilizing targeted yoga techniques to address each of the five koshas, considering their physical and mental makeup.

Review of Literature

To enhance sattva (equilibrium), Patil and Nagendra (2014) used an Integral Yoga module that included a combination of asanas, pranayama, chanting, Nadanusandhana, and games. They discovered that doing this kind of integral yoga significantly increases sattva guna while decreasing rajas and tamas guna. The psychological aspects of yoga, however, have received less attention in most of these investigations. Putra (2016) effectively employed a variety of yoga-based psychological elements, including lifestyle modification, notions of happiness, action motivation, and other elements, to improve sattva in one study.

In addition to the neurobiological effects that may be responsible for these improvements, Varambally and Gangadhar (2012) found that yoga can result in notable symptomatic improvements in psychiatric diseases. This implies that mental health practitioners ought to be receptive to the potential advantages of spiritual practices for their patients, either as stand-alone treatments for specific conditions or as adjuncts to contemporary therapies.

In patients with chronic low back pain (CLBP), Tekur, Nagarathna, Chametcha, Hankey, and Nagendra (2012) discovered that a seven-day intensive residential yoga program increases spinal mobility and lowers pain, anxiety, and depression more efficiently than physiotherapy treatments.

Agrawal (2021) has employed Sattva Enhancement Therapy, a psychotherapy practice rooted in Indian psychology, with a client. Following a thematic study of the Patanjali Yoga sutra, Yoga Vasishtha, and Bhagavad-Gita, a heuristic model of therapeutic approach was developed, with six interconnected themes serving as the focus of intervention. One 68-year-old man who presented with feelings of despair, wrath, bitterness, and guilt was successfully treated with this method.

Yoga is regarded by Husain (2011) as a spiritual exercise. Yoga incorporates mental, spiritual, and physical exercises to improve and preserve mental, spiritual, and physical health. Yoga enhances cerebral performance and cultivates spiritual energy through physical postures and breathing techniques. Yoga takes a holistic approach, with the asanas and niyamas serving as the foundation for spiritual growth, which in turn supports human wellness on all levels. Yogic activities are beneficial in meeting people's physical and emotional requirements and desires.

Several studies have documented the therapeutic impact of Yoga in emotional regulation, mood stabilization, and anxiety reduction. Kirkwood et al. (2005) studied the benefits of yoga in reducing depression. Smith et al. (2007) showed the benefits of yoga and relaxation in reducing stress and anxiety. Kaur et al. (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study to compare cognition, coping styles and Vedic personality among individuals practicing different lifestyles and found that yoga practitioners had a distinctly higher sattva guna and preferentially recruited brain areas associated with self-regulation and inhibitory control.

The connection between Jyotisha, Vastu Shastra, and Samudrika Shastra and psychology, mental health, and the psyche is examined by Naveen Pant (2024). The study investigates the connection between astrology and sexuality. Astronomy, astrology, and time measurement based on celestial body motions are the main topics of Jyotisha, a branch of Hindu knowledge.

Indian astrology has a strong emphasis on mental health and the mind, and it has been suggested that astrology can help treat mood and personality issues. The study of home architecture and the totality of energies and powers evoked by a private structure's size, shape, and geometry as well as its dynamic interactions with the surroundings, is known as Vastu Shastra. The study examines Samudrika Shastra's conception of psychology and mental health as well as the potential for scientific research on astrological and sexual elements. The study emphasizes how important it is to consider these conventional domains when discussing the mind, psychology, sexuality, and mental health.

According to Sharma and Sanal (2025), the integration of Ayurvedic and Jyotish principles reveals that personalized, time-

sensitive treatment plans can address both physical and karmic health challenges. The synergy of planetary influences with the Ayurvedic dosha framework creates a more nuanced and precise approach to health care, particularly for chronic and lifestyle-related conditions. The cosmic influence provides additional depth in therapy selection, enhancing outcomes where conventional treatments might not be enough.

The potential for Vedanta to foster psychological well-being and social harmony has been explored by several philosophers. Rao and Paranjpe (2008) believe that psychological issues are at the base of Advaita and in a significant sense constitute its core.

Nidhi (2025) has observed that holistic mental well-being is possible through the integration of Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and the ancient Vedic wisdom of the Advait Vedanta (principle of Non-Duality of the Individual Reality & Universal Reality). This integration guides positive mental health and well-being.

The reviewed literature highlights the potential benefits of integrating Vedic counselling into modern psychotherapy, emphasizing its holistic approach to mental health and well-being. Studies suggest that incorporating yoga, Ayurveda, and Vedanta principles can positively impact psychological disorders, while also promoting overall wellness. However, there's a need for more research on the awareness and application of Vedic counselling among psychotherapists. The current study aims to bridge this gap by assessing the awareness and willingness of psychotherapists to integrate Vedic counselling into their practice.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the level of awareness of Vedic Counselling among Psychotherapists and Counsellors
- To assess the willingness among psychotherapists to integrate Vedic Counselling to manage various psychological disorders

Method

Participants

25 male and female /practicing Psychologists in the age group of 35 to 45 years in Bangalore city were included in the sample. All the counsellors had 8 to10 years of counselling experience. They have been working on individual clients, adolescents, adult and geriatric populations. The survey questions were based on the five aspects of Vedic Counselling (Yoga, Vedanta, Ayurveda, Jyotish, & Vastu)

Research Design

Survey research is used in this study.

Measure

A survey questionnaire was used for the interview.

Focus group discussion was carried out to explore the views of the participants regarding Vedic counselling

The following are a few questions from the survey.

- As a Psychologist and a Counsellor, do you apply Vedic Counselling /Karmic Counselling with your Clients?
- What are the mental health conditions where the application of Vedic Counselling has proved beneficial?
- On what age groups do you think Vedic Counselling will prove beneficial?

- Do you recommend Yoga asanas in your psychotherapy?
- Do you incorporate Ayurvedic diet advice in counselling?
- Do you believe in Jyotish or Astrology as a means of finding solutions to the problems of your clients?
- Do you believe in Vastu shastra in terms of contributing to mental health and advising your clients in modifying the immediate environment for psychological well-being?
- Do you use inspiring stories from ancient Indian scriptures to motivate your clients?
- What form of Psychotherapy do you practice?
- Do you recommend some of your clients to a trained Vedic Counsellor?

Statistical Analysis

Percentage analysis was done. The responses were qualitatively analysed

Procedure

Data was collected by meeting the counsellors and giving them the survey questions. Data was also collected by small focus group discussions and interaction with each of the counsellors. Their responses were analyzed for the themes of belief, application, life modification and consistency. Their responses for the four aspects of Vedic counselling such as Yoga and Meditation, Ayurveda, Jyotishya, and Vastu shastra were analyzed thematically.

Results

Table 1

Awareness and Willingness of Psychotherapists towards Vedic Counselling

Aspects of Vedic Counselling	Awareness	Willingness to Apply
Yoga and Meditation	100%	100%
Ayurveda	80%	60%
Vedanta	60%	20%
Jyotish Shastra	40%	16%
Vastu Shastra	20%	0%

Table 2

Benefits of Vedic Counselling in Psychological Disorders

Psychological Disorder	Benefits of Vedic Counselling
Anxiety Disorders	Yoga and meditation reduce anxiety symptoma
Personality disorders	Yoga and meditation improve emotional reactions

Discussion

The awareness of *Vedic* counselling among the Psychotherapists and counsellors was analysed and the willingness to integrate it in psychotherapy is discussed. Most of the psychotherapists practiced Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) on their patients. Few also used Client-centered approach, Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy (REBT), Trauma-informed practices like integral somatic psychology and internal family systems approach. However, as integrative therapists, they also work towards physical, emotional, cognitive, social, and spiritual well-being of the client according to the needs of the client.

Yoga and Meditation- all the psychotherapists strongly recommend yoga and meditation for their clients. Some trained their

clients on their own and some referred them to yoga therapists. There is complete awareness about the positive effects of yoga and the several breathing exercises on the mental health of the patients. This was strongly recommended for patients with anxiety disorders and depression. Few patients with personality disorders such as Paranoid personality disorders and Borderline Personality Disorders benefitted from it. Most therapists extensively incorporate yoga asanas and pranayama to establish a healthy self-care routine and a healthy lifestyle in their clients. This finding is in keeping with the previous studies which have documented the therapeutic impact of Yoga in emotional regulation, mood stabilization, and anxiety reduction. Kirkwood et al. (2005) studied the benefits of yoga in reducing depression. Smith et al. (2007) showed the benefits of yoga and relaxation in reducing stress and anxiety.

Ayurveda- Though the therapists did not recommend Ayurvedic treatment for mental health conditions, they did advise their patients regarding Satvik diet, which would enable them to calm themselves and have better digestion and mood. They would generally advise them not to indulge in processed food, reach out to fresh fruits and vegetables, get more fresh air, rise early and keep physically active. Many CBT practitioners incorporated food journaling along with thought and emotion journaling. All of them are aware of the Triguna and Tridoshas but do not want to delve deep into them. The diet therapy was particularly useful for patients with depression, poor body image, psychosomatic disorders, children with ADHD and Learning Disabilities. Most counsellors are aware of the gut-brain axis and how gut issues can affect thoughts and emotions and counsel their patients in this regard. According to Sharma and Sanal (2025), the integration of Ayurvedic and Jyotish principles reveals that personalized, time-sensitive treatment plans can address both physical and karmic health challenges. In this survey, while awareness is high, there is a 20% drop in willingness to apply it. This may be due to the fact that Ayurveda involves dietary and physical treatments that fall outside the typical scope of "talk therapy."

Jyotish Shastra- Of the 25 counsellors interviewed only 4 showed belief in the science of Astrology or Jyotish Shastra. However, they did not incorporate it into their therapy or refer their clients to any astrologers but would listen to the clients' beliefs in Jyotish nonjudgmentally. But the concept of Karma would be discussed and in some cases of trauma and abuse, there was a need to understand that we do not have control over certain situations in life. The locus of control in the patients was discussed. Most clients are influenced by their cultural thoughts, which are usually social appropriations rather than an authentic understanding of cultural intelligence and philosophy. Belief in Karma is a means of rationalizing for many clients to cope with setbacks or failures in life.

Karma theory enables empowerment and accountability towards one's actions and one's responses to life's challenges. The belief in karma is seen in clients across various religions and age groups. Some clients as young as 20 years also resign themselves to the doings of fate and feel better with these thoughts. Awareness of astrology among the counsellors is relatively low, and willingness to use it is even lower, reflecting a significant skepticism toward integrating divination or planetary influences into modern psychology.

Vastu Shastra- People in their environment are under more stress than ever before due to modern living. Family and work-related stress is rising everywhere we look, and we are more vulnerable to hypertension, stress, anguish, rage, misery, and hostility. Everyone in

the community is searching for various ways to relieve stress, whether it be financial, marital, emotional, spiritual, physical or any other social or psychological issues. By using Vastu principles wisely, we may protect ourselves from these bad influences, enhance our quality of life, and foster harmony, prosperity, serenity, happiness, mental calm, and spiritual development.

However, none of the psychotherapists were open to the understanding of Vastu shastra and directional science. The closest suggestion they would give was in terms of modifying the immediate environment if it was interfering with their activities but the belief in Vastu remedies for psychological difficulties was totally absent. Most therapists believe that the immediate environment has a huge impact on psychological well-being and work with clients on how they would choose to modify their immediate environment in terms of being close to nature and five elements. This indicates that psychotherapists do not currently see a clinical link between spatial design and psychological well-being.

Vedanta- Out of 25 psychotherapists, 5 of them used stories from the ancient Indian scriptures in their therapy. Most believed it would be unprofessional and unscientific to narrate stories from the scriptures. The few psychotherapists who used storytelling as a strategy were consistent in their use of stories from the ancient scriptures. The psychospiritual counselling helped several client to resolve conflicts. However, this represents the largest gap in the dataset. Although 60% of therapists understand Vedantic philosophy (which deals with the nature of existence & the self), only 20% feel comfortable or willing to integrate these philosophical tenets into their counselling sessions.

By using Vastu principles wisely, we may protect ourselves from these bad influences, enhance our quality of life, and foster harmony, prosperity, serenity, happiness, mental calm, and spiritual development. However, none of the psychotherapists were open to the understanding of Vastu shastra and directional science. The closest suggestion they would give was in terms of modifying the immediate environment if it was interfering with their activities but the belief in Vastu remedies for psychological difficulties was totally absent. Most therapists believe that the immediate environment has a huge impact on psychological well-being and work with clients on how they would choose to modify their immediate environment in terms of being close to nature and five elements. This indicates that psychotherapists do not currently see a clinical link between spatial design and psychological well-being.

This chart effectively highlights the gap between professional knowledge and clinical application across various branches of Vedic counselling. The downward trend in the graph suggests that as the subjects move from physical/mental practices (Yoga) toward

philosophical (Vedanta) or environmental/metaphysical (Vastu) ones, professional acceptance drops sharply.

Conclusion

The objectives of the present study were to assess the level of awareness among counsellors and psychologists regarding Vedic Counselling and their willingness to apply it in practice. The following conclusions are made.

- Most of the Counsellors who participated in this study are aware of the 5 aspects of Vedic counselling, which are Yoga and Meditation, Vedanta, Jyotish Shastra, Ayurveda and Vastu Shastra.
- They were open to incorporating yoga and meditation in their practice and to a certain extent, ayurvedic diet for certain patients.
- However, the willingness to apply Jyotish shastra, Vastu shastra and narrating stories from the Vedanta is completely lacking.
- Along with evidence-based psychotherapy, integrating aspects of Vedic counselling by counsellors in India could be beneficial in treating several psychological and lifestyle disorders.
- Training the counsellors in Yoga, meditation and Vedantic understanding of Psychology of human behaviour would contribute to holistic well-being of their clients.
- To improve patient care, expert guidance, government and non-government initiatives are required to revitalize this resurging field of psychotherapy.

When comparing modern psychotherapies with Indian philosophical, ayurvedic, and Vedic concepts, the main issue is that while modern psychotherapy is disorder-oriented and illness-focused, ancient Indian concepts deal with universal moral commandments and self-discipline to lead a balanced life. It is necessary to comprehend the Vedic principles of psychological well-being, which include mastering the art of proper intention, cultivating the capacity for concentration and focus, and learning to use the mind's strength. Guiding counsellors in this area would contribute to physical and emotional well-being of individuals seeking mental health support.

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Received February 10, 2026

Revision received March 6, 2026

Accepted March 10, 2026